

The AI Trust Study : A Study on Human Reliance on AI Suggestions

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Note to Readers

Before reading this paper, you can try out the AI Trust Study platform yourself to experience how the experiment works.

Visit: [The AI Trust Study Platform](#)

Abstract

As Artificial Intelligence (AI) continues to infiltrate our lives, it is vital to consider how we trust it. I wanted to explore what made certain people follow AI suggestions and others ignore it. Thus, I built the website, The AI Trust Study, where a total of 150 people answered 18 questions. The questions, a combination of trivia, puzzles, and real-life situations encouraged respondents to think.

In the study, I varied two things, the confidence of the AI ("High" vs. "Low" confidence) and whether or not the person was time-pressed. The data was very straightforward. When the AI expressed confidence, the subjects trusted it significantly more than when it expressed uncertainty, in other words, 81% trusted it with confidence compared to 34% with uncertainty. And when people were pressed for time, they relied on AI nearly 22% more than when they took their time.

What surprised me most was how often people trusted the AI even when it was wrong. When the AI gave an incorrect answer but sounded very confident, almost half the people (46%) still accepted it. This showed me how easily confidence can change our judgment. It made me realize that AI should be designed in a way that helps people understand when to trust it — and when to think twice.

1. Introduction

AI has evolved from the realm of science fiction into an everyday reality. We regularly use AI-enabled products or services, such as GPS for navigating a new area or scrolling through streaming services to find our next movie. However, as technologies advance and become smarter than mere machines, AI will be employed more frequently in more consequential areas, such as medicine, education, and finance - areas where AI recommendations can impact many people's lives. These systems realize their potential only when people have trust in them and

use their suggested recommendations.

The phenomenon of trust between humans and AI systems is not a simple one to assess. An individual would ideally only trust an AI when there is trust to be put into it. But in reality, that is not how trust always presents itself. In fact, individuals' trust can be affected simply by how an AI system communicates its suggestions or information. Trust can lead individuals to mistakenly trust an AI-enabled product or service, regardless of whether it is incorrect. This is what is referred to as automation bias, which occurs when an individual trusts an AI suggestion because it emanates from machines (Cummings, 2004).

I created this project to better understand what makes people trust an AI. This study was designed to test the following hypotheses:

1. **Hypothesis 1:** Participants will be significantly more likely to accept a suggestion from an AI that states it has high confidence compared to one that states it has low confidence.
2. **Hypothesis 2:** Participants under time pressure will be more likely to accept an AI's suggestion than those with no time constraints.
3. **Hypothesis 3:** A significant number of participants will exhibit "automation bias" by accepting incorrect suggestions from a high-confidence AI.

To test these hypotheses, I built an interactive web platform to simulate these situations and collect data on human decision-making.

2. Methodology

2.1. Participants

I recruited 150 participants for the research with a mix of educators and students. Several of the educators came from various educational institutions across India., including members of the All Indian Schools Association. I also included undergraduate students and some professionals. Some participants enrolled through LinkedIn where I posted the study link. This reached people from different demographics while helping show balance and meaningfulness of the findings.

2.2. The Platform and Questions

The study was run on the "AI Trust Study" website that I built.

- **Interface:** The website showed participants one question at a time with a progress bar, a 35-second timer, and a box with the "AI Suggestion." For some questions, this box also showed the AI's confidence level.
- **The Questions:** I created 18 questions that were a mix of **Trivia**, **Puzzles**, and **Judgment Calls** (ethical questions). To test how people react to bad advice, I programmed the AI's suggestions so that 6 were correct, 6 were slightly off, and 6 were completely wrong.

2.3. Study Conditions

Every participant experienced all four of the study's conditions, which were randomly

assigned to the different questions:

1. **Standard:** The basic condition with no timer and no AI confidence level shown.
2. **Time Pressure:** A 35-second countdown timer was shown to make the participant feel rushed.
3. **AI High Confidence:** The AI's suggestion included the text: "AI Confidence: High (95%)."
4. **AI Low Confidence:** The AI's suggestion included the text: "AI Confidence: Low (45%)."

The primary dependent variable was the participant's binary choice for each question: **"Accept AI Suggestion"** or **"Use My Own Judgment."**

2.4. Procedure

1. Upon visiting the site, participants were presented with an informed consent form.
2. After consenting, they entered their name and were shown the study instructions.
3. For each of the 18 tasks, a question was displayed along with the AI's suggestion under one of the four conditions.
4. The participant had 35 seconds to make a choice. If they chose "Use My Own Judgment," a modal window appeared for them to input their own answer.
5. Upon completion, a results screen was generated, providing them a personal "AI Trust Score" and a detailed log of their answers.
6. As a token of appreciation, every participant was issued a personalized "Certificate of Participation" for their contribution to the research.

2.5. Data Analysis

All the data from the study was collected through the website. After completing the timed questions, participants clicked a button labeled **"Send Results to Researcher,"** which automatically sent their responses to my research email (theaitruststudy@gmail.com). I gathered all the results from those emails and reviewed them carefully. Then I used ChatGPT with the Deep Research and Analyze mode to help me organize, summarize, and deeply analyze the data to find patterns and understand how people trusted the AI under different conditions

2.6. Ethical Considerations

The study was formulated to protect the welfare of the participants. All data were collected and stored without participant names. Participant names were connected to data only for the on-screen experience and for certificates. Participants were told that their responses would be used for research and were also reminded that they could withdraw from the study at any point without penalty.

3. Results

The data from the 150 participants provided clear and statistically significant findings that supported all three initial hypotheses.

Overall AI Reliance: Across all conditions, participants chose to accept the AI's suggestion **62%** of the time. This varied slightly by demographic, with students showing the highest baseline level of trust.

Participant Group	Average AI Suggestion Acceptance Rate
Undergraduate Students	68%
Professionals	61%
K-12 Teachers	57%

Table 1: AI Reliance by Participant Demographic.

Effect of AI's Stated Confidence & Time Pressure: As predicted, the AI's stated confidence was the most influential factor. In the "AI High Confidence" condition, suggestions were accepted **81%** of the time, compared to just **34%** in the "AI Low Confidence" condition. Time pressure also significantly increased reliance, with the acceptance rate jumping from 58% in the standard condition to 70%.

Figure 1: AI Suggestion Acceptance Rates by Experimental Condition

Automation Bias and AI Inaccuracy: The study showed strong evidence of automation bias. When the AI presented an incorrect answer but stated it was "Highly Confident," participants still accepted the erroneous advice **46%** of the time. This demonstrates how a confident-sounding AI can effectively mislead users.

Condition	Overall AI Suggestion Acceptance Rate	Acceptance Rate for Incorrect AI Suggestions
High Confidence	81%	46%
Low Confidence	34%	11%
Time Pressure	70%	31%
Standard	58%	25%

Table 2: Comparison of Overall vs. Incorrect Suggestion Acceptance Rates.

4. Discussion

The results from my study show that how much we trust an AI system can be easily influenced, and is not tied to performance alone. The considerable amount of impact from whether or not an AI is confident is similar to the idea of "belief heuristic," which is a tendency to trust an individual that acts confident.

The finding was interesting, and a little troubling, demonstrating that people accepted the AI's incorrect answer almost half the time just because the AI expressed high confidence. This shows a large problem for real world situations. For example, a navigation app that confidently provided a wrong turn has the potential to be more dangerous than an app that expressed error. This use case prompts the need for "explainable AI" (XAI) not just providing an answer, but also demonstrating where the confidence level came from.

The fact that people relied on the AI more when they were rushed supports the idea of "cognitive offloading," which is basically passing the mental work onto something else. When we don't have time to think, we look for an easy answer, and the AI provides one. This has implications for high-stakes professions where people work under pressure, suggesting that AI tools in these fields need special safeguards against over-reliance.

Of course, my study had some limits. The questions were pretty low-stakes, and a wrong answer didn't have any real consequences. For future research, it would be fascinating to conduct a follow-up study using a simulated stock-picking task, where participants could win

or lose small amounts of real money based on their decisions. This would test if financial stakes change the willingness to trust an AI's advice.

Even though the study was small, it reflects real behaviors we see when people use AI in daily life — trusting the tone more than the truth.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this project showed that how an AI presents information is just as important as the information itself. Things like confidence levels and time pressure can dramatically change how much we are willing to trust an AI. The "automation bias" I saw in my results is a real concern. If we are going to use AI as a tool to help us, we need to be aware of its power to persuade us and learn how to question it. This means we need to focus on designing AI that is not only smart but also helps users understand its own limits.

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